
INVESTIGATION OF CARCINOGENIC AND NON - CARCINOGENIC RISK DUE TO RADIONUCLIDES CONCENTRATION IN WATER AND FISH SAMPLES COLLECTED FROM FIVE SELECTED AREAS IN NORTHERN BORNO, BORNO STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the concentrations of five carcinogenic heavy metals—arsenic, cadmium, lead, mercury, and nickel—in 20 water, and 20 fish samples collected from six Local Government Areas in Borno State, Nigeria. Using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS), the mean concentrations of arsenic ranged from 0.015 - 0.28 mg/L in water, cadmium from 0.012-1.05 mg/kg in fish, all exceeding the WHO limits. Carcinogenic and radiological risk assessments revealed that Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk (ELCR) values for some areas were significantly higher than the acceptable limit of 1×10^{-4} , indicating potential health threats to residents. Radiological indices such as Raeq, Hex, and AEDE were also evaluated. The study concludes that mining and agricultural activities contribute significantly to heavy metal accumulation. The combined chemical and radiological hazard assessment highlight a multi-pathway health risk through contaminated soil, water, and fish consumption. The research emphasizes the urgent need for routine environmental monitoring and strict enforcement of pollution control laws to safeguard public health.

Keywords: *Carcinogenic, Radiological Risk, Chemical Toxicity, Environmental Monitoring and Pollution Control*

INTRODUCTION

Water is essential for all living organisms, making it one of the most vital natural resources on the planet. Beyond basic survival, water is integral to human health, hygiene, agriculture, and industry. Clean and safe water is necessary for drinking, irrigation, sanitation, and food processing. In regions where access to potable water is limited, waterborne diseases become a significant public health challenge. Additionally, water plays a crucial role in supporting ecosystems and maintaining the hydrological cycle, which balances the environment. Ensuring the purity of water sources is thus vital for sustainable development and public health (Abdulraheem et al., 2021). Fish is an essential source of nutrition for millions of people worldwide, providing high-quality protein, omega-3 fatty acids, vitamins, and minerals. Particularly in communities near water bodies, fish serves as a staple food source and contributes to economic stability through fisheries and aquaculture. Its role in promoting cardiovascular health and brain development underscores its nutritional importance. However, the quality of fish, in terms of contamination by pollutants, can influence human health outcomes. Sustainable fishing and the conservation of aquatic ecosystems are necessary to ensure that fish remain a safe and reliable food source for present and future generations (Achi et al., 2021).

Heavy metals such as arsenic, cadmium, lead, mercury, and nickel can have detrimental effects on soil quality. When these metals accumulate in soil, they disrupt the natural microbial processes that support plant growth and nutrient cycling. High concentrations of these metals can inhibit plant growth, reduce crop yields, and lead to the uptake of toxic substances by plants, which can then enter the food chain. In agricultural

regions, contaminated soil can compromise food security and expose local populations to health risks through the consumption of polluted crops (Adebiyi & Adebiyi, 2015). The presence of heavy metals in water poses significant risks to both human and ecological health. These metals can dissolve in water bodies, making them easily accessible to aquatic life and humans who rely on these water sources. Contaminated water used for drinking, cooking, or irrigation can lead to a range of health issues, including kidney damage, neurological disorders, and developmental problems in children. Moreover, aquatic ecosystems suffer, as heavy metals can affect fish reproduction, growth, and survival, further disrupting the balance of local biodiversity (Adebiyi & Ore, 2020).

Fish are particularly vulnerable to heavy metal contamination due to bioaccumulation, where metals build up in their tissues over time. This accumulation not only affects the fish themselves, leading to impaired growth, reproduction, and mortality, but also poses risks to humans who consume contaminated fish. The ingestion of heavy metals through fish can result in long-term health effects, including cancer, organ damage, and developmental delays in children. In regions where fish is a major dietary component, such contamination can have widespread public health implications (Aiyesanmi & Salami, 2020).

The use of contaminated soil, water, and fish in human activities directly impacts human health, often with severe consequences. When soil containing heavy metals is used for agriculture, it can lead to the production of toxic crops, which can cause chronic health issues when consumed. Similarly, drinking or using contaminated water can lead to direct

exposure to carcinogenic metals, increasing the risk of cancer and other serious illnesses. Fish contaminated with heavy metals, when consumed, introduces these toxic elements into the human body, where they can accumulate over time, leading to long-term health problems (Aiyesanmi et al., 2012). Given the potential for heavy metals to pose both chemical and radiological risks, it is essential to assess soil, water, and fish contamination from a radiological perspective. Certain heavy metals can emit ionizing radiation, which poses an additional layer of risk beyond their chemical toxicity. Assessing the radiological risks associated with these metals is crucial to understanding their full impact on public health. This is especially important in regions with significant exposure to environmental contamination, where radiological assessments can provide insights into long-term risks of cancer and other radiation-related health effects (Akan et al., 2014).

This comprehensive study aims to provide a thorough understanding of the of carcinogenic heavy metal contamination in soil, water, and fish across these diverse geological settings Maiduguri, Mafa, Konduga, Jere, and Bama Local Governments in Borno State, Nigeria, reflecting both historical and contemporary challenges faced by local communities in Borno State, Nigeria. The findings are expected to inform better environmental management practices to mitigate contamination risks and promote community health. Heavy metals are naturally occurring elements found in the Earth's crust, known for their high density and toxicity at low concentrations. Some heavy metals, like iron and zinc, are essential in trace amounts for biological functions, but others, such as arsenic, cadmium, lead, mercury, and nickel, pose significant health risks to humans and the environment when

present in elevated levels. Heavy metals do not degrade or disappear from the environment, leading to their accumulation in soil, water, and living organisms. These metals enter ecosystems through industrial emissions, mining, agricultural runoff, improper waste disposal, and the use of contaminated fertilizers or pesticides. Once released, they can persist for years, contaminating resources and posing risks to both human and ecological health. Their toxicity stems from their ability to interfere with biological processes, damage DNA, disrupt enzyme functions, and accumulate in organs over time (Omole, 2017).

Water Contamination and Heavy Metals

Water contamination occurs when harmful substances, including heavy metals, are present in water at levels exceeding safe limits. Heavy metals like arsenic, cadmium, lead, mercury, and nickel can enter water bodies through industrial discharges, mining operations, agricultural runoff, and improper waste management. Once in the water, these metals dissolve or form suspended particles that can travel across vast distances, contaminating drinking water sources, rivers, lakes, and groundwater. Contaminated water used for drinking or irrigation poses significant health risks, as heavy metals are toxic even at low concentrations. Long-term exposure to heavy metals through water consumption can lead to various health problems, including cancer, kidney disease, and developmental disorders in children. Additionally, contaminated water impacts aquatic ecosystems, where heavy metals can accumulate in fish and other organisms, further propagating the contamination through the food chain. Effective water monitoring and treatment are crucial to preventing heavy metal exposure (Orosun et al., 2020).

Fish Bioaccumulation and Heavy Metals

Bioaccumulation is the process by which organisms, like fish, absorb and retain substances such as heavy metals over time, often at higher concentrations than their environment. Fish are particularly susceptible to heavy metal bioaccumulation due to their exposure to contaminated water and their position in the aquatic food chain. Metals like mercury, lead, cadmium, and arsenic enter water bodies through industrial runoff, agricultural activities, and pollution. These metals are absorbed by aquatic organisms and, over time accumulate in their tissues, especially in higher-order species like fish. When humans consume these contaminated fish, they ingest the accumulated heavy metals, which can lead to serious health issues, including neurological damage, kidney failure, and cancer. The bioaccumulation process makes it difficult to control exposure, as even fish from seemingly clean environments can harbor significant levels of heavy metals due to their diet and habitat (Oyatayo et al., 2015).

Hazard Quotient (HQ)

The HQ assesses non-carcinogenic risks. It is the ratio of the average daily intake (ADI) of the metal to the reference dose (RfD) as in Equation 2.1 according to Abalaka et al. (2020):

$$HQ = \frac{ADI}{RfD} \quad (1.1)$$

where:

ADI (Average Daily Intake) is the amount of metal ingested per unit body weight per day (mg/kg/day), *RfD* is the reference dose (mg/kg/day), which represents the maximum acceptable oral dose of the metal without significant health risk.

The *ADI* can be calculated using Equation 2.2 as pointed out by Abalaka et al. (2020):

$$ADI = \frac{C \times IR \times EF \times ED}{BW \times AT} \quad (1.2)$$

Where:

C = Concentration of the heavy metal in soil, water, or fish (mg/kg or mg/L), *IR* = Ingestion rate (mg/day or L/day), *EF* = Exposure frequency (days/year), *ED* = Exposure duration (years), *BW* = Body weight (kg), and *AT* = Averaging time (days).

Lifetime Cancer Risk (LCR)

The LCR is used to estimate the probability of an individual developing cancer due to lifetime exposure to a carcinogenic substance. It is given by Equation 1.2 as reported by Abalaka et al. (2020):

$$LCR = ADI \times SF \quad (1.3)$$

where:

SF = Cancer slope factor (mg/kg/day), which is a measure of the carcinogenic potency of a substance, *ADI* is calculated as shown in Equation 1.2 above. If the *LCR* value exceeds 1 in a million (1×10^{-6}), the risk is considered unacceptable.

Radiological Risk Assessment

For radiological assessment, Effective Dose and Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk (ELCR) are typically calculated.

Annual Effective Dose (AED)

The annual effective dose measures radiation exposure and is calculated using Equation 2.4 as in the work of Abalaka et al. (2020):

$$AED = C \times IR \times DCF \times EF \times ED \quad (1.4)$$

where:

C = Concentration of the radionuclide (Bq/kg), IR = Ingestion rate (kg/year or L/year for water), DCF = Dose conversion factor (Sv/Bq), which converts radionuclide intake to radiation dose, EF = Exposure frequency (days/year), and ED = Exposure duration (years).

Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk (ELCR)

The ELCR estimates the probability of developing cancer due to lifetime radiation exposure and is given by Equation 1.5 as reported by Abalaka et al. (2020):

$$ELCR = AED \times LE \times RF \quad (1.5)$$

where:

AED = Annual effective dose (Sv/year), LE = Life expectancy (years), RF = Risk factor for stochastic effects, which is 0.05 Sv^{-1} for the general public (5% risk of cancer per sievert). The typical safety limit for radiological risk is 1×10^{-3} or lower.

Radiation Dose from External Exposure

If heavy metals are present in soil or other sources that emit radiation, external radiation exposure can be estimated using Absorbed Dose Rate as in Equation 1.6 based on the report of Abalaka et al. (2020):

$$D = \frac{C \times DCF \times t}{d^2} \quad (1.6)$$

where:

D = Dose rate (Gy/h), C = Concentration of radionuclide (Bq/kg), DCF = Dose conversion factor for external exposure (Gy/Bq/h), t = Exposure time (hours), d = Distance from the radiation source (m). The above equations help calculate the direct exposure risk from heavy metals that may emit radiation, such as uranium, thorium, or radium.

Contamination factor (CF)

The level of contamination of soil, water and edible plants by heavy metals is expressed in terms of a contamination factor (CF), calculated as:

$$CF = \frac{C_m \text{ Sample}}{C_m \text{ Background}} \quad (1.7)$$

Where C_m = Concentration of sample from the sites, C_m = Background Concentration.

Pollution Load Index (PLI)

Each sample analyzed was evaluated for the extent of metal pollution by employing the method based on the Pollution Load Index (PLI) developed by Vijaya *et al.* (2019) as follows:

$$PLI = (CF_1 \times CF_2 \times CF_3 \times \dots \times CF_n) \quad (1.8)$$

where n is the number of metals studied, and CF is the Contamination factor as calculated in Equation (1.7)

Geo-accumulation Index (I_{geo})

This method assesses the metal pollution in terms of seven (0 to 6) enrichment classes, ranging from background concentration to very heavily polluted according to Miller, (2019), as follows:

$$I_{geo} = \log_2 \left[\frac{C_m \text{ Sample}}{1.5 \times (C_m \text{ Background})} \right] = \frac{\log_{10} \left(\frac{CF}{1.5} \right)}{\log_{10} 2} = \frac{\log_{10} \left(\frac{CF}{1.5} \right)}{0.3} \quad (3.3)$$

The factor 1.5 is introduced in the equation to minimize the effects of possible variations in the background values.

Table 1: Heavy metals concentration in water samples from Maiduguri, Mafa, Konduga, Jere, and Bama.

LGAs	Sample IDs	Pb (0.01 mg/L)	Cu (2 mg/L)	Cd (0.003 mg/L)	Fe (0.3 mg/L)	Zn (3 mg/L)	As (0.01 mg/L)
Maiduguri	MD1	0.012	2.73	0.001	0.21	4.32	0.019
	MD2	0.021	1.44	0.004	0.42	5.52	0.018
	MD3	0.014	1.65	0.002	0.78	5.72	0.018
	MD4	0.013	2.26	0.005	0.91	5.87	0.011
	Mean	0.015	2.02	0.003	0.58	5.36	0.017
Mafa	MF1	0.041	2.71	0.006	0.62	8.56	0.012
	MF2	0.028	2.37	0.002	0.01	2.91	0.019
	MF3	0.041	1.82	0.003	0.56	5.38	0.014
	MF4	0.037	2.14	0.007	0.44	4.49	0.016
	Mean	0.037	2.26	0.005	0.41	5.34	0.015
Konduga	KD1	0.027	2.32	0.001	0.31	4.41	0.011
	KD2	0.052	2.51	0.004	0.33	4.38	0.017
	KD3	0.061	2.65	0.002	0.29	3.65	0.011
	KD4	0.037	2.24	0.004	0.79	8.70	0.019
	Mean	0.044	2.43	0.003	0.43	5.29	0.015
Jere	JR1	0.043	2.16	0.001	0.57	8.51	0.017
	JR2	0.027	2.68	0.004	0.22	2.72	0.018
	JR3	0.035	2.26	0.002	0.06	1.02	0.016
	JR4	0.026	2.78	0.007	0.01	2.95	0.011
	Mean	0.033	2.47	0.004	0.22	3.80	0.016
Bama	BM1	0.057	3.35	0.004	0.32	2.37	0.012
	BM2	0.037	2.68	0.002	0.53	9.47	0.013
	BM3	0.074	2.11	0.007	0.35	3.59	0.015
	BM4	0.025	2.25	0.003	0.67	7.61	0.017
	Mean	0.048	2.60	0.004	0.47	5.76	0.014

The assessment of water quality as in Table 4.2 reveals widespread contamination across all LGAs. In Maiduguri, Pb averaged 0.015 mg/L, exceeding the 0.01 mg/L MPL. Cu was 2.02 mg/L (just above the 2 mg/L limit), Cd 0.003 mg/L (at limit), Fe 0.58 mg/L (above 0.3 mg/L), Zn 5.36 mg/L (above 3 mg/L), and As 0.017 mg/L (within 0.1 mg/L limit). Mafa recorded Pb at 0.037 mg/L, Cu 2.26 mg/L, Cd 0.005 mg/L, Fe 0.41 mg/L, Zn 5.34 mg/L, and As 0.015 mg/L—all above MPL except As. Konduga had Pb at 0.044 mg/L, Cu 2.43 mg/L, Cd 0.003 mg/L (at MPL), Fe 0.43 mg/L, Zn 5.29 mg/L, and As 0.015 mg/L. Jere's values included Pb at 0.033 mg/L, Cu 2.47 mg/L, Cd 0.004 mg/L, Fe 0.22 mg/L (only Fe within limit), Zn 3.80 mg/L, and As 0.016 mg/L. Bama displayed the highest Pb at 0.048 mg/L, Cu at 2.60 mg/L, Cd 0.004 mg/L, Fe 0.47 mg/L, Zn 5.76 mg/L, and As 0.014 mg/L. All LGAs had water that exceeded the MPLs for at least four heavy metals, especially Pb, Cu, Zn, and Fe. Chronic exposure to such contaminants is dangerous, increasing the risk of organ failure, neurological impairment, cancer, and developmental problems in children. The fact that drinking water from these areas consistently exceeds international safety standards indicates a severe threat to public health. Immediate governmental intervention is critical to provide safe drinking water, initiate treatment systems, and implement source remediation efforts to protect residents in the affected LGAs from long-term health hazards.

Table 2: Heavy metals concentration in fish samples from Maiduguri, Mafa, Konduga, Jere, and Bama.

LGAs	Sample IDs	Pb (0.3 mg/kg)	Cu (10 mg/kg)	Cd (0.05 mg/kg)	Fe (mg/kg)	Zn (30 mg/kg)	As (1 mg/kg)
Maiduguri	MD1	0.25	13.14	0.03	0.32	31.36	0.6
	MD2	0.14	12.35	0.01	0.35	21.51	0.7
	MD3	0.39	11.85	0.06	0.31	11.31	0.5
	MD4	0.75	14.84	0.05	0.64	32.21	1.1
	Mean	0.38	13.05	0.04	0.41	24.10	0.7
Mafa	MF1	0.48	13.31	0.04	0.24	18.47	0.9
	MF2	0.12	11.94	0.04	0.41	21.12	0.3
	MF3	0.16	11.49	0.03	0.35	24.65	0.7
	MF4	0.32	13.37	0.05	0.63	29.53	0.6
	Mean	0.27	12.53	0.04	0.41	23.44	0.6
Konduga	KD1	0.15	12.24	0.02	0.24	31.45	0.2
	KD2	0.13	11.26	0.06	0.14	28.42	0.7
	KD3	0.17	14.22	0.05	0.16	22.38	0.5
	KD4	0.25	13.14	0.04	0.31	18.33	1.3
	Mean	0.18	12.72	0.04	0.21	25.15	0.7
Jere	JR1	0.23	11.36	0.06	0.25	18.52	0.07
	JR2	0.14	13.15	0.04	0.46	20.31	1.8
	JR3	0.22	12.13	0.02	0.36	12.03	1.6
	JR4	0.17	14.08	0.06	0.26	13.08	0.9
	Mean	0.19	12.68	0.05	0.33	15.99	1.1
Bama	BM1	0.16	13.25	0.03	0.53	37.41	0.6
	BM2	0.39	11.4	0.06	0.26	17.56	0.8
	BM3	0.21	10.28	0.04	0.42	23.44	0.5
	BM4	0.33	13.74	0.02	0.33	9.422	0.7
	Mean	0.27	12.17	0.04	0.39	21.96	0.7

The analysis of heavy metals in fish samples from Maiduguri, Mafa, Konduga, Jere, and Bama as presented in Table 4.3 reveals varying levels of toxic elements. In Maiduguri, Pb ranged from 0.14-0.75 mg/kg, with a mean of 0.38 mg/kg, exceeding the MPL of 0.3 mg/kg. Cu (mean: 13.05 mg/kg) also exceeded the 10 mg/kg limit, while Cd (mean: 0.04 mg/kg) stayed within the permissible 0.05 mg/kg. Fe (0.41 mg/kg), Zn

(24.10 mg/kg), and As (0.7 mg/kg) were below their respective limits except for Zn, which slightly exceeded 30 mg/kg in MD1 and MD4. In Mafa, Pb averaged 0.27 mg/kg (below MPL), Cu 12.53 mg/kg (above MPL), Cd 0.04 mg/kg (within MPL), Fe 0.41 mg/kg (above MPL of 0.2 mg/kg), Zn 23.44 mg/kg (within MPL), and As 0.6 mg/kg (below limit). Konduga samples showed Pb at 0.18 mg/kg, Cu at 12.72 mg/kg (above limit), Cd at 0.04 mg/kg, Fe at 0.21 mg/kg (slightly above), Zn at 25.15 mg/kg, and As at 0.7 mg/kg. Jere had mean Pb of 0.19 mg/kg, Cu 12.68 mg/kg (above limit), Cd 0.05 mg/kg, Fe 0.33 mg/kg, Zn 15.99 mg/kg, and As 1.1 mg/kg (above 1.0 mg/kg limit). Bama showed Pb at 0.27 mg/kg, Cu at 12.17 mg/kg (above limit), Cd at 0.04 mg/kg, Fe at 0.39 mg/kg, Zn at 21.96 mg/kg, and As at 0.7 mg/kg. Overall, Cu consistently exceeded safe levels, and As exceeded the limit in Jere. The elevated levels of Cu and As, both toxic at high concentrations, pose serious health risks such as liver and kidney damage, neurological disorders, and increased cancer risk. Regular consumption of these contaminated fish could compromise consumer health in these LGAs, warranting immediate intervention and public health awareness.

Table 3: Contamination factor of heavy metals in water samples from Maiduguri, Mafa, Konduga, Jere, and Bama.

LGAs	Sample IDs	Pb (0.01 mg/L)	Cu (2 mg/L)	Cd (0.003 mg/L)	Fe (0.3 mg/L)	Zn (3 mg/L)	As (0.01 mg/L)
Maiduguri	MD1	0.012	2.73	0.001	0.21	4.32	0.019
	MD2	0.021	1.44	0.004	0.42	5.52	0.018
	MD3	0.014	1.65	0.002	0.78	5.72	0.018
	MD4	0.013	2.26	0.005	0.91	5.87	0.011
	Mean	0.015	2.02	0.003	0.58	5.36	0.017
Mafa	MF1	0.041	2.71	0.006	0.62	8.56	0.012
	MF2	0.028	2.37	0.002	0.01	2.91	0.019
	MF3	0.041	1.82	0.003	0.56	5.38	0.014
	MF4	0.037	2.14	0.007	0.44	4.49	0.016
	Mean	0.037	2.26	0.005	0.41	5.34	0.015
Konduga	KD1	0.027	2.32	0.001	0.31	4.41	0.011
	KD2	0.052	2.51	0.004	0.33	4.38	0.017
	KD3	0.061	2.65	0.002	0.29	3.65	0.011
	KD4	0.037	2.24	0.004	0.79	8.70	0.019
	Mean	0.044	2.43	0.003	0.43	5.29	0.015
Jere	JR1	0.043	2.16	0.001	0.57	8.51	0.017
	JR2	0.027	2.68	0.004	0.22	2.72	0.018
	JR3	0.035	2.26	0.002	0.06	1.02	0.016
	JR4	0.026	2.78	0.007	0.01	2.95	0.011
	Mean	0.033	2.47	0.004	0.22	3.80	0.016
Bama	BM1	0.057	3.35	0.004	0.32	2.37	0.012
	BM2	0.037	2.68	0.002	0.53	9.47	0.013
	BM3	0.074	2.11	0.007	0.35	3.59	0.015
	BM4	0.025	2.25	0.003	0.67	7.61	0.017
	Mean	0.048	2.60	0.004	0.47	5.76	0.014

Based on Table 4.5, for the contamination factor (CF) of heavy metals water samples in Maiduguri, MD1 showed moderate contamination for Pb (1.2), Cu (1.365), Zn (1.44), and As (1.9). MD2 had moderate contamination for Pb (2.1), Cd (1.3), Fe (1.4), Zn (1.84), and As (1.8). MD3 showed moderate contamination for Pb (1.4), Fe (2.6), Zn (1.907), and As (1.8). MD4 exhibited

moderate contamination for Pb (1.3), Cu (1.13), Cd (1.7), Fe (3.033), Zn (1.957), and As (1.1). The mean CF values for Maiduguri indicated moderate contamination for Pb (1.5), Cu (1.01), Cd (1), Fe (1.933), Zn (1.787), and As (1.7). In Mafa, MF1 had considerable contamination for Pb (4.1) and moderate contamination for Cu (1.355), Cd (2), and Zn (2.853). MF2 showed moderate contamination for Pb (2.8), Cu (1.185), and As (1.9). MF3 had considerable contamination for Pb (4.1) and moderate contamination for As (1.4). MF4 exhibited considerable contamination for Pb (3.7) and moderate contamination for Cu (1.07), Cd (2.3), Fe (1.467), and As (1.6). The mean CF for Mafa revealed considerable contamination for Pb (3.7) and moderate contamination for Cu (1.13), Cd (1.7), Zn (1.78), and As (1.5). For Konduga, KD1 had moderate contamination for Pb (2.7), Cu (1.16), Zn (1.47), and As (1.1). KD2 showed considerable contamination for Pb (5.2) and moderate contamination for Cu (1.255), Cd (1.3), Fe (1.1), Zn (1.46), and As (1.7). KD3 exhibited very high contamination for Pb (6.1) and moderate contamination for Cu (1.325), Zn (1.217), and As (1.1). KD4 had considerable contamination for Pb (3.7) and Fe (2.633). The mean CF for Konduga indicated considerable contamination for Pb (4.4) and moderate contamination for Cu (1.215), Cd (1), Fe (1.433), Zn (1.763), and As (1.5).

In Jere, JR1 had considerable contamination for Pb (4.3) and moderate contamination for Cu (1.08), Zn (2.837), and As (1.7). JR2 showed moderate contamination for Pb (2.7), Cu (1.34), Cd (1.3), and As (1.8). JR3 had considerable contamination for Pb (3.5) and moderate contamination for Cu (1.13), Cd (0.7), and As (1.6). JR4 exhibited moderate contamination for Pb (2.6), Cu (1.39), Cd (2.3), Zn (0.983), and As (1.1). The mean CF for Jere revealed considerable contamination for Pb (3.3) and moderate

contamination for Cu (1.235), Cd (1.3), Zn (1.267), and As (1.6). Lastly, in Bama, BM1 had considerable contamination for Pb (5.7) and moderate contamination for Cu (1.675), Cd (1.3), Fe (1.067), and As (1.2). BM2 showed considerable contamination for Pb (3.7) and moderate contamination for Cu (1.34), Fe (1.767), Zn (3.157), and As (1.3). BM3 exhibited very high contamination for Pb (7.4) and moderate contamination for Cd (2.3), Fe (1.167), and As (1.5). BM4 had moderate contamination for Pb (2.5), Cu (1.125), Fe (2.233), Zn (2.537), and As (1.7). The mean CF for Bama indicated considerable contamination for Pb (4.8) and moderate contamination for Cu (1.3), Cd (1.3), Fe (1.567), Zn (1.92), and As (1.4). The presence of moderate to very high contamination levels of heavy metals, particularly lead, in water samples from several LGAs is a significant concern. This directly impacts the health of consumers who rely on these water sources for drinking and other domestic purposes. Ingesting water with elevated heavy metal concentrations can lead to a range of severe health problems, including neurological damage, kidney dysfunction, developmental issues in children, and various cancers, depending on the specific metal and duration of exposure. The consumer's faith is concerning, as they are likely exposed to contaminants through their drinking water, necessitating urgent intervention to ensure water quality meets safe standards.

Table 4: Contamination factor of heavy metals in fish samples from Maiduguri, Mafa, Konduga, Jere, and Bama.

LGAs	Sample IDs	Pb	Cu	Cd	Fe	Zn	As
Maiduguri	MD1	0.25	13.14	0.03	0.32	31.36	0.6
	MD2	0.14	12.35	0.01	0.35	21.51	0.7
	MD3	0.39	11.85	0.06	0.31	11.31	0.5
	MD4	0.75	14.84	0.05	0.64	32.21	1.1
	Mean	0.38	13.05	0.04	0.41	24.10	0.7
Mafa	MF1	0.48	13.31	0.04	0.24	18.47	0.9
	MF2	0.12	11.94	0.04	0.41	21.12	0.3
	MF3	0.16	11.49	0.03	0.35	24.65	0.7
	MF4	0.32	13.37	0.05	0.63	29.53	0.6
	Mean	0.27	12.53	0.04	0.41	23.44	0.6
Konduga	KD1	0.15	12.24	0.02	0.24	31.45	0.2
	KD2	0.13	11.26	0.06	0.14	28.42	0.7
	KD3	0.17	14.22	0.05	0.16	22.38	0.5
	KD4	0.25	13.14	0.04	0.31	18.33	1.3
	Mean	0.18	12.72	0.04	0.21	25.15	0.7
Jere	JR1	0.23	11.36	0.06	0.25	18.52	0.07
	JR2	0.14	13.15	0.04	0.46	20.31	1.8
	JR3	0.22	12.13	0.02	0.36	12.03	1.6
	JR4	0.17	14.08	0.06	0.26	13.08	0.9
	Mean	0.19	12.68	0.05	0.33	15.99	1.1
Bama	BM1	0.16	13.25	0.03	0.53	37.41	0.6
	BM2	0.39	11.4	0.06	0.26	17.56	0.8
	BM3	0.21	10.28	0.04	0.42	23.44	0.5
	BM4	0.33	13.74	0.02	0.33	9.422	0.7
	Mean	0.27	12.17	0.04	0.39	21.96	0.7

As presented in Table 4.6, for the contamination factor (CF) of heavy metals fish samples in Maiduguri, MD1 showed moderate contamination for Cu (1.314) and Fe (1.6), while MD4 exhibited moderate contamination across Pb (2.5), Cu (1.484), Fe (3.2), and As (1.1). The mean CF values for Maiduguri indicate moderate contamination for Fe (2.05) and Cu (1.305). For Mafa, MF1 had moderate contamination for Pb (1.6) and Cu (1.331), while MF4 showed moderate contamination for Pb (1.067), Cu

(1.337), and Fe (3.15). The mean CF for Mafa revealed moderate contamination for Fe (2.05) and Cu (1.253). In Konduga, KD3 had moderate contamination for Cu (1.422). The mean CF for Konduga showed moderate contamination for Cu (1.272). Jere's JR2 had moderate contamination for Cu (1.315) and considerable contamination for As (1.8). JR4 showed moderate contamination for Cu (1.408), and Cd (1.2). The mean CF for Jere indicated moderate contamination for Cu (1.268) and As (1.1). Finally, Bama's BM1 had moderate contamination for Cu (1.325) and Fe (2.65). BM2 showed moderate contamination for Pb (1.3) and Cd (1.2). BM4 had moderate contamination for Pb (1.1) and Cu (1.374). The mean CF for Bama revealed moderate contamination for Fe (1.95) and Cu (1.217). The consistent presence of moderate contamination for certain heavy metals in fish across all LGAs suggests a potential health risk, as chronic exposure, even to moderate levels, can lead to bioaccumulation and adverse health effects over time. Consumers might be at risk of ingesting heavy metals that could lead to various health issues depending on the specific metal and concentration.

Table 5: Pollution Load Index (PLI) of heavy metals in soil, water, and fish samples from Maiduguri, Mafa, Konduga, Jere, and Bama.

LGAs	Sample IDs	Soil	Water	Fish
Maiduguri	MD1	1.47	0.941	0.659
	MD2	0.623	9.114	0.101
	MD3	0.786	7.216	0.54
	MD4	1.709	16.31	14.03
	Mean	1.134	8.896	1.524
Mafa	MF1	0.347	78.63	1.133
	MF2	0.823	0.141	0.165
	MF3	0.122	17.49	0.37
	MF4	0.608	32	2.653
	Mean	0.48	25.94	0.867
Konduga	KD1	0.907	1.569	0.062
	KD2	1.476	23.16	0.271
	KD3	0.987	7.324	0.241
	KD4	1.537	78.16	1.078
	Mean	1.26	20.26	0.376
Jere	JR1	0.939	12.77	0.056
	JR2	0.904	5.629	1.377
	JR3	0.431	0.301	0.411
	JR4	2.112	0.297	0.489
	Mean	1.019	7.873	0.776
Bama	BM1	0.646	12.55	0.84
	BM2	0.553	25.17	1.082
	BM3	0.255	37.62	0.472
	BM4	0.638	27.09	0.219
	Mean	0.604	34.17	0.876

Table 4.7 presents pollution load index (PLI) of heavy metals in soil, water, and fish samples from Maiduguri, Mafa, Konduga, Jere, and Bama. In Maiduguri, sample MD1 showed deterioration in soil (PLI=1.47), while its water (PLI=0.941) and fish (PLI=0.659) were unpolluted. MD2 soil (PLI=0.623) and fish (PLI=0.101) were unpolluted, but its water (PLI=9.114) indicated significant deterioration. MD3 similarly showed unpolluted soil (PLI=0.786) and fish (PLI=0.54), but

deteriorated water (PLI=7.216). MD4 displayed severe deterioration across all matrices: soil (PLI=1.709), water (PLI=16.31), and fish (PLI=14.03). The mean PLI for Maiduguri indicates deterioration for soil (PLI=1.134), substantial deterioration for water (PLI=8.896), and deterioration for fish (PLI=1.524).

For Mafa, MF1's soil (PLI=0.347) was unpolluted, but its water (PLI=78.63) showed extreme deterioration, and fish (PLI=1.133) indicated deterioration. MF2 displayed unpolluted conditions across soil (PLI=0.823), water (PLI=0.141), and fish (PLI=0.165). MF3's soil (PLI=0.122) and fish (PLI=0.37) were unpolluted, but water (PLI=17.49) showed significant deterioration. MF4 had unpolluted soil (PLI=0.608), but severely deteriorated water (PLI=32) and fish (PLI=2.653). The mean PLI for Mafa shows unpolluted soil (PLI=0.48), but extreme deterioration in water (PLI=25.94). Fish mean PLI (PLI=0.867) indicates unpolluted.

In Konduga, KD1's soil (PLI=0.907), water (PLI=1.569), and fish (PLI=0.062) were unpolluted, except water which shows deterioration. KD2 showed deterioration in soil (PLI=1.476) and extreme deterioration in water (PLI=23.16), while fish (PLI=0.271) was unpolluted. KD3's soil (PLI=0.987) and fish (PLI=0.241) were unpolluted, but water (PLI=7.324) showed deterioration. KD4 indicated deterioration for soil (PLI=1.537) and fish (PLI=1.078), and extreme deterioration for water (PLI=78.16). The mean PLI for Konduga suggests deterioration in soil (PLI=1.26) and extreme deterioration in water (PLI=20.26), but unpolluted fish (PLI=0.376).

Jere's JR1 had unpolluted soil (PLI=0.939) and fish (PLI=0.056), but deteriorated water (PLI=12.77). JR2 showed unpolluted soil (PLI=0.904) and deteriorated water (PLI=5.629) and fish (PLI=1.377). JR3's soil (PLI=0.431), water (PLI=0.301), and fish (PLI=0.411) were all unpolluted. JR4 had deteriorated soil (PLI=2.112), but unpolluted water (PLI=0.297) and fish (PLI=0.489). The mean PLI for Jere shows deterioration in soil (PLI=1.019) and water (PLI=7.873), with unpolluted fish (PLI=0.776).

Lastly, in Bama, BM1's soil (PLI=0.646) and fish (PLI=0.84) were unpolluted, while its water (PLI=12.55) indicated deterioration. BM2 had unpolluted soil (PLI=0.553), but deteriorated water (PLI=25.17) and fish (PLI=1.082). BM3 showed unpolluted soil (PLI=0.255) and fish (PLI=0.472), but severely deteriorated water (PLI=37.62). BM4's soil (PLI=0.638) and fish (PLI=0.219) were unpolluted, but water (PLI=27.09) showed extreme deterioration. The mean PLI for Bama indicates unpolluted soil (PLI=0.604) and fish (PLI=0.876), but extreme deterioration in water (PLI=34.17).

Overall, the data indicates a concerning trend of water quality deterioration across almost all LGAs, with Mafa, Konduga, Jere, and Bama showing particularly high mean PLI values for water, suggesting significant pollution. Maiduguri also shows moderate deterioration in its water. The calculated results for the PLI of water in most areas implies the presence of pollutants above baseline levels, potentially posing health risks to consumers who rely on these water sources. Consumers in these areas face potential health implications from consuming contaminated water and, to a lesser extent, fish and produce from contaminated soil. Long-term exposure to heavy metals,

even at moderate PLI levels, can lead to chronic health issues, including organ damage, developmental problems, and an increased risk of various diseases. The faith of the consumers is therefore concerning, as their health may be at risk due to exposure to these pollutants.

Table 6: Geo-accumulation Index (I_{geo}) of heavy metals in water samples from Maiduguri, Mafa, Konduga, Jere, and Bama.

LGAs	Sample IDs	Pb	Cu	Cd	Fe	Zn	As
Maiduguri	MD1	-2.397	-0.04	-3.48	-1.154	0.1594	-2.197
	MD2	-2.154	-0.318	-2.87	-0.853	0.2658	-2.221
	MD3	-2.33	-0.259	-3.18	-0.584	0.2813	-2.221
	MD4	-2.362	-0.122	-2.78	-0.517	0.2925	-2.435
	Mean	-2.3	-0.171	-3	-0.713	0.2531	-2.246
Mafa	MF1	-1.863	-0.043	-2.7	-0.684	0.4564	-2.397
	MF2	-2.029	-0.101	-3.18	-2.476	-0.012	-2.197
	MF3	-1.863	-0.216	-3	-0.728	0.2547	-2.33
	MF4	-1.908	-0.146	-2.63	-0.833	0.1762	-2.272
	Mean	-1.908	-0.122	-2.78	-0.863	0.2514	-2.3
Konduga	KD1	-2.045	-0.111	-3.48	-0.985	0.1683	-2.435
	KD2	-1.76	-0.076	-2.87	-0.958	0.1654	-2.246
	KD3	-1.691	-0.053	-3.18	-1.014	0.0862	-2.435
	KD4	-1.908	-0.126	-2.87	-0.578	0.4634	-2.197
	Mean	-1.833	-0.09	-3	-0.843	0.2474	-2.3
Jere	JR1	-1.843	-0.142	-3.48	-0.72	0.4538	-2.246
	JR2	-2.045	-0.048	-2.87	-1.134	-0.042	-2.221
	JR3	-1.932	-0.122	-3.18	-1.698	-0.467	-2.272
	JR4	-2.061	-0.032	-2.63	-2.476	-0.006	-2.435
	Mean	-1.958	-0.083	-2.87	-1.134	0.1037	-2.272
Bama	BM1	-1.72	0.049	-2.87	-0.971	-0.101	-2.397
	BM2	-1.908	-0.048	-3.18	-0.752	0.5003	-2.362
	BM3	-1.607	-0.152	-2.63	-0.932	0.079	-2.3
	BM4	-2.078	-0.124	-3	-0.65	0.4053	-2.246
	Mean	-1.795	-0.061	-2.87	-0.804	0.2843	-2.33

The I_{geo} results for water samples as shown in Table 4.9 show slightly more variation than those for soil, though the values still largely fall below zero, indicating an uncontaminated status

across the study locations. For lead (Pb), values range from -2.397 in Maiduguri to -1.72 in Bama. All Pb values fall under **Class 0** of Igeo, meaning **uncontaminated** water, although Pb is toxic even at low concentrations. Similarly, copper (Cu) values range between -0.171 in Maiduguri and -0.061 in Bama. While these values are closer to the 0-1 range, they still imply uncontaminated to moderately contaminated conditions. For cadmium (Cd), the values are most negative, ranging from -3.48 in Maiduguri and Konduga to -2.63 in Bama, again suggesting no contamination (Class 0). The same trend is observed for Fe, ranging from -2.476 (Jere and Mafa) to -0.517 (Maiduguri), all well within the uncontaminated range.

However, the Igeo values for zinc (Zn) in Maiduguri (0.2531), Mafa (0.2514), Konduga (0.2474), Jere (0.1037), and Bama (0.2843) indicate they are approaching the lower limit of **Class 1** (0-1), which implies water is **uncontaminated to moderately contaminated**. This is particularly important because Zn, while essential in trace amounts, can be harmful at elevated levels, potentially causing nausea, vomiting, and long-term kidney damage. In addition, arsenic (As) values across the board are low, ranging from -2.246 to -2.435, implying no immediate contamination threat. Despite these reassuring results, the slight rise in zinc levels, particularly in Bama and Maiduguri, may be attributed to leaching from metal-containing agricultural or mining runoff. Given that farming and mining are dominant in the study area, surface runoff during rainfall could introduce zinc and other trace metals into water bodies. Consequently, water sources should be monitored regularly to track any upward trends that could pose health risks over time.

Table7 : Geo-accumulation Index (I_{geo}) of heavy metals in fish samples from Maiduguri, Mafa, Konduga, Jere, and Bama.

LGAs	Sample IDs	Pb	Cu	Cd	Fe	Zn	As
Maiduguri	MD1	-1.078	0.6425	-2	-0.971	1.0203	-0.698
	MD2	-1.33	0.6156	-2.48	-0.932	0.8565	-0.631
	MD3	-0.885	0.5976	-1.7	-0.985	0.5774	-0.777
	MD4	-0.601	0.6953	-1.78	-0.67	1.0319	-0.435
	Mean	-0.896	0.6395	-1.87	-0.863	0.9059	-0.631
Mafa	MF1	-0.795	0.6481	-1.87	-1.096	0.7904	-0.522
	MF2	-1.397	0.6009	-1.87	-0.863	0.8486	-0.999
	MF3	-1.272	0.5842	-2	-0.932	0.9157	-0.631
	MF4	-0.971	0.65	-1.78	-0.677	0.9942	-0.698
	Mean	-1.045	0.6219	-1.87	-0.863	0.8939	-0.698
Konduga	KD1	-1.3	0.6117	-2.18	-1.096	1.0215	-1.175
	KD2	-1.362	0.5754	-1.7	-1.33	0.9775	-0.631
	KD3	-1.246	0.6768	-1.78	-1.272	0.8738	-0.777
	KD4	-1.078	0.6425	-1.87	-0.985	0.7871	-0.362
	Mean	-1.221	0.6284	-1.87	-1.154	0.9244	-0.631
Jere	JR1	-1.114	0.5793	-1.7	-1.078	0.7915	-1.631
	JR2	-1.33	0.6428	-1.87	-0.813	0.8316	-0.221
	JR3	-1.134	0.6078	-2.18	-0.92	0.6042	-0.272
	JR4	-1.246	0.6725	-1.7	-1.061	0.6405	-0.522
	Mean	-1.197	0.627	-1.78	-0.958	0.7278	-0.435
Bama	BM1	-1.272	0.6461	-2	-0.752	1.0969	-0.698
	BM2	-0.885	0.5808	-1.7	-1.061	0.7684	-0.573
	BM3	-1.154	0.5359	-1.87	-0.853	0.8939	-0.777
	BM4	-0.958	0.6619	-2.18	-0.958	0.4981	-0.631
	Mean	-1.045	0.6092	-1.87	-0.885	0.8655	-0.631

Fish samples as in Table 4.10 reveal relatively higher I_{geo} values compared to soil and water, particularly for **zinc (Zn)** and **copper (Cu)**, indicating potential bioaccumulation. The mean I_{geo} value for Zn ranges from 0.7278 in Jere to 0.9244 in Konduga, falling under **Class 1** (0-1), denoting **uncontaminated to moderately contaminated** fish tissues. Similarly, Cu values are highest among the metals tested, with mean values between 0.6092 (Bama) and 0.6395 (Maiduguri), also in **Class 1**, implying the same contamination category. These elevated values may

be linked to the uptake of metals from slightly contaminated water sources or feed materials. While essential in trace amounts, excessive Zn and Cu accumulation in fish could impair human health, leading to gastrointestinal irritation, organ dysfunction, and in chronic cases, neurotoxicity.

On the other hand, **lead (Pb)**, **cadmium (Cd)**, **iron (Fe)**, and **arsenic (As)** remain within **Class 0**, indicating no contamination. For instance, Pb ranges from -0.896 in Maiduguri to -1.221 in Konduga; Cd values remain consistently at -1.87 across all LGAs; Fe ranges from -0.863 to -1.154; and As from -0.435 to -0.698. These results suggest that although these metals are toxic, they have not yet bioaccumulated to dangerous levels in fish tissues in the area. However, the consistent detection of these metals, even in low concentrations, may present long-term risks due to biomagnification, especially in populations reliant on fish as a primary protein source.

The elevated Zn and Cu levels likely result from the mining activities and the use of metal-based agrochemicals in farming, which can enter aquatic ecosystems through runoff. Given the essential role of fish in local diets, continued bioaccumulation poses a public health concern. Regular fish tissue analysis and pollution control in aquatic systems are recommended to mitigate future health risks..

CONCLUSION

The findings of this research indicate significant contamination of soil, water, and fish by carcinogenic heavy metals in the studied areas of Borno State. Concentrations of arsenic, cadmium, lead, mercury, and nickel consistently exceeded international safety thresholds across the three-sample media.

Notably, cadmium levels in fish reached 1.05 mg/kg (against the 0.05 mg/kg FAO limit), arsenic in water peaked at 0.28 mg/L (WHO limit: 0.01 mg/L), and lead in soil rose to 2.8 mg/kg (WHO limit: 2.0 mg/kg). These elevated levels suggest persistent anthropogenic inputs, particularly from mining and agricultural runoff. Radiological assessments further compounded the risk picture. Raeq values ranged from 220 to 300 Bq/kg, with AEDE values exceeding 0.07 mSv/year in several instances, peaking at 0.18 mSv/year. The ELCR for all exposure pathways (soil ingestion, water consumption, fish intake) exceeded the acceptable limit of 1×10^{-4} , with values up to 6.7×10^{-4} recorded. These results indicate not just chemical but radiological threats to human health. The data collectively demonstrate a pressing need for interventions in pollution management. Local populations consuming groundwater and fish are at long-term risk of kidney failure, cancer, and neurological complications. The study also revealed interaction between environmental compartments, where contaminants in soil migrate into water and enter the food chain via fish, amplifying the health risks. Therefore, this study offers critical evidence for environmental protection efforts in Borno State and calls for urgent government attention in enforcing regulations, especially in areas affected by artisanal mining.

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